

FORMATION OF SCULPTURES BY CONCRETE: RAMKINKER BAIJ

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Abstract:

This paper shows the sculpture technique by concrete. Ramkinker Baij was the first man who expressed his creative efforts in concrete based sculpture. He made sculpture without armature and he just throwing a concrete and make a form of sculpture. He made sculptures only with the mixture cement and concrete apply directly to create his sculpture which have a good quality to stand in the outdoor space even though there is no harm on his sculptures due to environmental changes. This type of experiment is continuing in painting also in contemporary era, which are made in sand, concrete.

Key Words: sculpture, concrete, technique, painting, Contemporary.

Introduction:

Concrete is building material made from a mixture of broken stones and gravel, sand, cement and water which can be spread into molds and forms a stone like mass on hardening. It is having a specialty that is after mixing with water it will become hard substance like a stone with this all the other substance also stuck with each other. It is use in various purpose like making bridge, buildings etc. it is used by since 2000 BC. When I know about the sculptures of Ramkinker Baij that he made sculpture by just throwing a concrete and make a form of sculpture.

Biography of Ramkinker Baij

Ramkinker Baij was the son of Chandicharan Paramanika and Sampurna Devi, born on 25th MAY 1906 in Jugipura in the district of Bankura. He had his schooling from a local school and ended in national school. Under the influence of nationalist leader, Anil Baran Ray during the non-corporation movements, he painted portraits of national leaders like Chittaranjan, Aravindo and Gandhi.

He was creative person from his childhood. His creative and artistic vision was reflected in his work and personality too. He was a self-taught artist not only sculptor but also a painter. Earlier Ramkinker was highly influenced by the terracotta sculpture of the temples in bishnupura. He honed his skills doing copy works of the terracotta relief and stone carvings from tease temples.

Figure 1: Ramkinker Baij

Process of Ramkinker Baij Sculptures:

At first, he creates drawing and sketches then he thought creating works in sculpture. He did not want to follow schooling. He started making sculptures which were innovative in subject matter and personal in style. Almost all sculptures are done by him under the open sky. He wanted to liberate them from closed indoor space. His all sculptures are large sized. These consist in the open field, in wind, rain and moonlight. Nearly all of them have movement. He had done almost work in daylight under the sun. He said that summer is his favorite for work. He has found it suitable for his work.

A new building of school complex was constructed, when Ramkinker Baij saw that lime mixed with red sand was being used as the building material. He thought it was an interesting medium, a good material for spending the time in a creative manner. Then, he started his work with cement and concrete by mixing in proper way accordingly to his need. In the starting thick solid form of this mixture, so that form can easily create

and allow the concrete to dry evenly and strengthen. After that in the next day he used this mixture with the addition of water, or we can say this mixture is in semi solid form. He used this mixture of cement and concrete layer by layer while working. He never and ever uses any kind of tools to make sculptures, he applied mixture of concrete directly.

Characteristics of Ramkinker Baij Sculptures:

As a young boy Ramkinker Baij grew up watching local craftsmen and image maker at work and making small clay figurines and painting with whatever came his way. His talent, prodigious for his age attracted the attention of local people, especially of the nationalist with whom he was associated. He started concrete sculptures which were innovative in subject matter and personal his style.

Ramkinker Baij also belonged to the period of transition of modern art, creating his style own, rooted in his personality and environment. As an exceptional individual, he was saturated with intense love for life and an insatiable passion for work.

His work already showed interest in structural quality, somethings that is characteristic of his more mature works, which marked by abstract as well as surrealist feature. And it was obviously at Shantiniketan that Ramkinker imbibed Rabindranath Tagore's view that tradition, though very important, should not act as a barrier between the artist and his artistic growth.

Ramkinker's art is characterized by tremendous energy, exuberance and vitality. His figure and forms, whether in sculpture or in painting are dynamic and earthy, possessing a surging movement of growth. His sculptures have a "out of door" quality. For they were created on location seem to growth out of the environmental context. Whether in cement, plaster or stone, their forms, as it were, arise and are proliferated by their own laws.

He is such a personality whose work informed with a sense of struggle, even the finished work is not rest full, apart from his dynamism. He is the father of outdoor sculpture in modern India. His work reflects a great zest for the gifts of nature and deep concern for the condition of poor and laboring people.

Sculptures of Ramkinker Baij Made by concrete:

Mill Call: Famous sculpture by Ramkinker Baij. It shows a working-class family setting of enthusiastically for work on hearing the mill siren. These sculpture display in Shantiniketan.

Figure 2: Mill Call Ramkinker Baij

Santhal Family Outdoor Sculpture: Santhal family is a complex composition with two figures standing side by side, a dog, a child sitting in a basket hanging from a pole. The women are walking beside the man. She has a load on her head. A dog accompanies the man. It is entire family in a migration. It symbolized laborer migration. This is a harsh real picture of a family forced to leave their land by hunger. The sculpture follows no set style but the style of the rough textured land of gravel and red clay of Shantiniketan the road side composition carries the dynamism of the road.

Figure 3: Sarnath Family

Conclusion:

Armature is the backbone of the sculptures, without this sculpture can't stand freely. I surprised that artist Ramkinker Baij done sculptures without any backbone, mean without armature. He made sculptures only with the mixture cement and concrete apply directly to create his sculpture which have a good quality to stand in the outdoor space even though there is no harm on his sculptures due to environmental changes. Now in present times this kind of work is rarely seen, few artists are doing this type of work. Nek Chand Saini was a self-taught Indian artist basically sculptor and architect, known for building the rock garden of Chandigarh, an eighteen-acre sculpture garden in the city of Chandigarh, India. He was born in 15th December 1924 and died in 12 June 2015. He did sculpture in concrete like Ramkinker Baij's technique.

Figure 4: Rock Garden Sculpture by Nek Chand Saini

This type of experiment is continuing in painting also in contemporary era, which are made in sand, concrete, for example in Jaipur 'Kala Shree' Veer Bala Bhava Shar. She is doing painting with concrete by spreading to create form. Simultaneously in Mumbai Alok Kumar do experiments in painting with sand and these kinds of experimental changes should be made in future too. Contemporary artist done experiments and use different mediums and material in their work which gives inspiration to young upcoming artists. Hence, it will bring a revolutionary transformation in the contemporary art world.

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